

Table 1: Project Profiles examples with their characteristics

Index	ID.Project	Application Domain	Used Technology	Application Type	Project Duration	Team Experience
0	P01	Education	.Net	Desktop	3 to 6	4 to 8
1	P02	Enterprise	JavaScript	Web	15 to 18	12 to 15
2	P03	Education	Python	Web	6 to 9	2 to 4
3	P04	Education	Python	Web	9 to 12	8 to 10
4	P05	Management and Business	Java	Desktop	9 to 12	10 to 12

Table 2: Characteristics vectors example generated based on characteristics extracted from a PA Target Project

	Application Domain	Used Technology	Application Type	Project Duration	Team Experience
p_a	1	1	1	1	1
p'_1	1	0	0	1	0
p'_2	1	1	0	0	0
p'_3	1	0	0	1	1
p'_4	0	1	0	1	0